

Author information

Name: Jente M. Houweling

Date: 2025-09-16

Title of manuscript: ToxTempAssistant: Using Large Language Models to Standardise Cell-Based Toxicological Test Method Descriptions

Contribution to the Publication

Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Data Curation, Visualisation, Writing - Original draft

Interests

Please select "Yes" or "No" next to any interests below that are relevant to your situation

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by your submitted publication?		Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by your submitted publication?	
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Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I declare a personal relationship with the second author of this manuscript.

Author information

Name: Matthias M. L. Arras

Date: 2025-09-16

Title of manuscript: ToxTempAssistant: Using Large Language Models to Standardise Cell-Based Toxicological Test Method Descriptions

Contribution to the Publication

Software, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualisation

Interests

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I declare a personal relationship with the main other and as a scientist working professionally with large language models, my contribution to the technical implementation arose naturally. Although I have left academia, I remain actively engaged in publishing, motivated by my continued interest in the academic process and in authoring scientific work.

Author information

Name: Egon L. Willighagen

Date: 2025-09-01

Title of manuscript: ToxTempAssistant: Using Large Language Models to Standardise Cell-Based Toxicological Test Method Descriptions

Contribution to the Publication

Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing - Review & Editing;

Interests

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LLMs are heavily debated in which I partake. I recently signed a Dutch letter against the uncritical adoption of LLMs (and other AI) at universities [0]. This public debate has a clear

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link to this paper, but they are not conflicting and I believe the debate helped the critical evaluation of this work. Specifically, publication or not of this paper does not neither affect other efforts in the past period nor in the next two years.

0. <https://openletter.earth/open-letter-stop-the-uncritical-adoption-of-ai-technologies-in-academia-b65bba1e>

Author information

Name: Danyel Jennen

Date: 2025-09-17

Title of manuscript: ToxTempAssistant: Using Large Language Models to Harmonise Cell-Based Toxicological Test Method Descriptions

Contribution to the Publication

Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing;

Interests

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Not Applicable

Author information

Name: Anne Kienhuis

Date: 2025-09-17

Title of manuscript: ToxTempAssistant: Using Large Language Models to Standardise Cell-Based Toxicological Test Method Descriptions

Contribution to the Publication

Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing.

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Author information

Name: Chris T. Evelo

Date: 2025-09-17

Title of manuscript: ToxTempAssistant: Using Large Language Models to Standardise Cell-Based Toxicological Test Method Descriptions

Contribution to the Publication

Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing - Review & Editing

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